

Summary Report of the NFDI4Earth Breakout Groups at the 1st NFDI4Earth Plenary Meeting (June 09-10, 2022)

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Executive Summary

The breakout groups during the NFDI4Earth plenary meeting (June 9-10, 2022 in Dresden) provided an opportunity for participants to share their ideas/wishes/feedback regarding NFDI4Earth. There were two types of breakout groups: task-area related and topic-related. This short report presents the key takeaways from the discussions done in the different groups. The minutes of the moderators of the different sessions are provided in the Appendix. At this stage, we take the opportunity to thank all participants, once again, for their active involvement¹!

¹Questions regarding this report should be addressed at Auriol Degbello (auriol.degbello@tu-dresden.de).

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Major takeaways from the task-area-related breakout groups

Note: whenever needs are mentioned in the summaries below, they are latent community needs, that is, they are mentioned from the point of view of a current or prospective user of NFDI4Earth.

Task Area 1, 2Participate: The discussion has highlighted two key needs from the participants: the need for better information about how to engage with NFDI4Earth (e.g. this could be done through a restructuring of the website, and/or a newsletter), and the need for a workflow that specifies how results from the pilots and incubators can be integrated with other products of NFDI4Earth.

Task Area 2, 2Facilitate: The need for offerings tailored to the background/skill levels of the NFDI4Earth users was mentioned during the discussion with the participants. Also, the discussion has reminded that the FAIR handling of large gridded datasets is challenging, and hence, there is a need for solutions to ease that task.

Task Area 3, 2Interoperate: The discussion has highlighted the need for KPIs (Key Performance Indicators) for the Knowledge Hub, the need for tools to make the services used (e.g. Knowledge Hub API) citable/acknowledgeable, and the need for a workflow to support the quality assurance of the NFDI4Earth products (e.g. metadata produced as input for the Knowledge Hub, and the Living Handbook).

Task Area 4, 2Coordinate: A key takeaway here was that the development of the services should work hand-in-hand with training. For example, the institutions of the co-apps/participants could integrate training about NFDI4Earth products into their teaching curriculum to promote their adoption by young researchers. As for the needs of the participants, one takeaway touched on information, in particular, better information about the central services offered by NFDI4Earth.

Major takeaways from the topic-related breakout groups

Note: the answers to the questions were varied. Listing all will overwhelm the reader, hence, we list up to three answers per question. The three answers were selected based on 1) the innovativeness of their content and 2) the potential impact of the implementation of the answer on research data management in the Earth Sciences. The full list of answers is available in the appendix (page 11).

Breakout Group 1, How do I see my institution positioned in the context of FDM and NFDI - where can NFDI4Earth help there?

- NFDI4Earth could help improve the visibility of tools, the visibility of guidance to use tools, and the visibility of services that facilitate research data management
- NFDI4Earth could help with education and training (e.g. provide easy workflows for resource contribution, their quality assurance/quality control, as well as training to facilitate their adoption)
- NFDI4Earth could help through the provision of linkage points (e.g. contact points for research data management) and support (e.g. the coupling of local user support networks with the NFDI4Earth user support network)

Breakout Group 2, What do I want for the (ESS) community (in terms of tools, support, teaching materials, etc.)?

Expectations regarding tools:

- Overview of what tools exist incl. some ranking
- Workflow/tools to reach data from the public industry
- Tools to combine FAIR teaching materials into a presentation

Expectations regarding support:

- Provide an exchange platform (like a forum) (as bottom-up), to
 - share experiences
 - find people with same idea, same skill set, same problem
 - meet for regular's table or group events
- Support server-side analysis and publishing
- Provide recommendations for datasets (recommendations should come from the community via a rating option)

Expectations regarding teaching materials:

- Provide FAIR teaching materials, which can be easily reused and (with resp. to infrastructure) easy to be combined

- Materials should be provided in video format, not just texts (because there are users that don't like to read long explanations)
- Include DM (Data Management) into Master/PhD courses

Breakout Group 3, What data and software 'products' do I envision in the NFDI4Earth?

Wishes regarding data

- Project-related datasets at research organizations (e.g. datasets / managed DBs produced in past research projects). These datasets are never going to get published (e.g. because funding for the project run out).
- Datasets from many regional data portals for which the awareness about their existence is still low
- High-resolution data that would be useful for research, but that for some reasons are not free of charge (e.g. 20cm satellite data)

Wishes regarding tools

- A virtual environment that supports reproducible publishing right at the beginning of scientific activities. For example, the data should be formatted for archiving before the analysis starts and the analysis is done in a private virtual environment. Once the research is completed (e.g. after the peer-review process), the researcher only switches the state of the virtual environment from "private" to "public" and the whole environment (data + tools) is made available to all
- Continuous integration (e.g. when the data is updated, update all services affected; changes on a GitHub/GitLab repository are automatically populated to the affected NFDI4Earth services)
- Tools to enable the (federated) search for software interfaces (e.g. APIs)

Breakout Group 4, What are the potential of and needs from Pilots, Incubators, EduTrain and Academy?

- Engagement possibilities need to be more clearly and broadly communicated in the ESS community
- Foster collaboration and engagement across ESS disciplines and other consortia

Breakout Group 5, If I could wish for an overarching theme for a pilot - what would it be?

Proposed Topics:

- Bridging NFDIs: interdisciplinary projects involving min. 2 consortia
- Combining datasets: different data centers; different formats or domains
- Provenance (reproducible workflows, data acquisition, ...)
- Visualisation of metadata and semantic data
- Mobilisation of data

Structural ideas:

- Split call: 1/2 thematic focus, 1/2 open call
- Flexfunds within Pilots for Spin-offs
- Future Rounds: use pilots to fill identified gaps within NFDI4Earth services

Breakout Group 6, What content would I like to see in the Interest Groups? Is what has been presented already sufficient - are we missing something?

- The Interest Groups should involve libraries
- Dealing with restrictive data (container solutions along the line of Ratswd)
- Instruments, samples and persistent identification

Appendix: Minutes from the task-area-related breakout groups

Task Area 1, 2Participate (Moderator: Veronika Grupp)

- Re-Design of 2Participate Homepage to present more clearly the different ways of engaging with NFDI4Earth (We had feedback that people are confused and unsure about how to engage)
- Need for a common strategy for public outreach to increase visibility
 - Publication of calls and their outcomes
 - Monitoring of outreach success
 - Establish a newsletter for interested people (for all TAs)
- Define strategy for continuation and integration of pilots and incubators
 - Decision on follow-up, what will future calls look like, evaluation criteria
 - How to deal with funding gaps? Search for fair solutions

Task Area 2, 2Facilitate (Moderator: Ivonne Anders)

M2.1 OneStop4All:

- We collected more user stories via the survey, but also within the breakouts!

M2.2:

- The support should have offers for the "different speeds" needed, especially also "easy-to-understand" offers, so that there are no fears of contact. "There are no stupid questions".
- Create communication channels needed with even more players than we have had in mind, e.g. libraries
- Build up subject-specific competence across all disciplines, methodological competence, we need to think about whether we should offer local support.

M2.4:

- A list of long-term archives will be compiled, contacted. Services, requirements and conditions will be compared.

M2.5:

- FAIR handling of large gridded datasets is challenging
- Our first task could be to publish a >1TB dataset in an existing cloud infrastructure incl. DOI as ARD
- There is a tension between requirements of long-term archiving and scientist persistence vs. agility/living datasets that we need to deal with

Task Area 3, 2Interoperate (Moderator: Stephan Frickenhaus)

Input from first day discussions:

- Need for KPIs (Key Performance Indicators) in KnowledgeHUB;
- Make the used service citable / acknowledgeable -> bibliometrics
- Create a PIXI-Book „Conny und der Data Cube“

First Input from Audience:

- Gap analysis via Pilots!
- Abstraction of pilot solutions to re-usable „patterns“
- Stakeholder-oriented workshops
- Monitor adoption of improved services

How do we interconnect to international activities?

- Identify points of interaction with EOSC in a targeted way
- Presence in user communities EGU/AGU etc.
- Fill gaps by proposals for projects with international activities
- Scaling up service usability along the subproject-subcommunity-national-international level (EOSC)
- Use information on engagement on European level
- Bridge to EOSC on high level/ N4E association (Verein)
- Take up services from EOSC instead of own re-implementation
- M3.2: export catalogues harvestable to EOSC or directly store in EOSC??

How does TA3 support Quality Assurance?

- Approach via crowd-sourced projects, e.g. Wikipedia
- Labelling process
- Collect user-feedback about the quality of metadata/ versioning
- Quality of Living Handbook (1% contributors vs. 99% users)
 - Fast and easy feedback texts on Wiki-pages or even on the page itself (“Was this page helpful?”)
 - Export the feedback to the providers
 - Fill-in boxes -> tickets for curators

How do we relate and interconnect to several existing services, e.g. re3data?

- If tagging „n4e“ is possible, other services should be used, like ZENODO

Task Area 4, 2Coordinate (Moderator: Auriol Degbelo)

This task area is responsible for the governance, cultural change and central services for the NFDI4earth. Below the main things learned and next steps.

- Governance: the steering Group is there, and the first meeting will take place before the Summer vacations. The group will initiate the needed steps to establish the advisory board. We need a new format for the bi-weekly co-apps meeting.
- Cultural change: we need to slowly get away from reputation and foster recognition. One open question at this point is: How to come from short-term projects to sustainable management of the research artifacts? Definition of the process to provide an NFDI4Earth badge for research projects could be one of the next steps. The development of the services should work hand-in-hand with training (e.g. at the institutions of

the co-apps and participants so that young researchers are exposed early to the 4Earth products).

- Central services: we've learned through the 2-day meeting that the offers from the central services are not entirely clear, and we should make some effort into explaining them better. Also, we should think together with the other TAs about integrating the outcomes of the Pilots/Incubators/Interest Groups into the products of 4Earth (One-Stop, KnowledgeHub).

Appendix: Minutes from the topic-related breakout groups

Breakout Group 1: How do I see my institution positioned in the context of FDM and NFDI - where can NFDI4Earth help there? [Moderators: Peter Braesicke, Thomas Rose].

- Sub-group 1
 - Contact point research data (local/regional) <-> NFDI4Earth
 - Visibility of tools / guidance / service
 - Example: Workflows for dataflows with QA/QC.
 - Can find community services, etc. ...
 - Liaison people (from central FDM).
 - Building "local" USNs - coupling to the NFDI4Earth USN.
 - Open software ... use services ...
 - Archiving ...
 - Pick up others ...
- Sub-group 2
 - Perspective HPC: User requirements ... input: Big data management
 - Is there enough local support?
 - Legal aspects ... work with public authorities ... (TA2, GDI-DE, Section-ELSA?)
 - Is sub-setting data RDM?
 - FAIR principles – who does the evaluation? (Criteria exist – I seems problematic) – some variety exist!
 - Challenge: Tools might set standards (or impose them) ... are the standards transferable? Central guidelines ...
- Sub-group 3
 - On the train ... Spread the word! Directors!
 - Role of libraries ... cultural change ...
 - Qualified staff ... not enough! Different demands ...
 - Different perspectives ...
 - Educational offers ... beyond institutions ...
 - Section-EduTrain – involve local Data Stewarts
 - Central RDM – sometimes not specific enough ... multipliers
 - Understanding cultural change ... qualification(s) through the local institution or through NFDI?
 - Top-down versus bottom-up ...
- Sub-group 4
 - Data Stewarts – some existing
 - Regionally strong expression - data aggregation across disciplines
 - Education and Training
 - Resources/infrastructure not always available (big data)
 - "Scaling" - Resolution (interoperability).
 - Linkage points and support from above
- Sub-group 5
 - NFDI(4Earth) is confusing ... :-)

- Institutes might not support contributions by individuals ...
- Top-down <-> bottom-up
- Research papers versus white papers, technical documentations
- Research versus infrastructure (raise profile)
- Mutual appreciation!
- Reputation: How should we call us?
- Sub-group 6
 - Section-EduTrain - transparent and obvious
 - University needs are clearer than what could be delivered ...
 - Platforms (make more visible/usable)
 - Have a say (address concretely in terms of feedback).
 - Credits (as measure of success) for decision makers (for further supporters)
 - Cooperation through feedback

Breakout Group 2: What do I want for the (ESS) community (in terms of tools, support, teaching materials, etc.)?

[Moderators: Ivonne Anders, Carsten Kessler, Sören Lorenz].

Below you will find answers or expectations or suggestions as to what the NFDI4Earth should achieve. The list will be used to create more user stories, which are urgently needed to develop and structure the various products of NFDI4Earth. This breakout was of high value for the next steps in the NFDI4Earth.

Answers and expectations:

Tools:

- Provide tools for server-side analysis and publishing
- Overview on what tools exist incl. some ranking
- To reach data from the public industry.
- Easy access to governmental data
- Tools or best practices for easy workflows (creation – storing – repositories – public authorities)
- Provide tools to combine FAIR teaching materials to e.g. a presentation
- Provide discipline specific tools for the same data or challenges
- Tools rating system

Support:

- establish support groups and expert groups for certain topics
- provide an exchange platform (like a forum) (as bottom up), to
 - share experiences
 - find people with same idea, same skill set, same problem
 - meet for regular's table or group events
- provide example workflows (to avoid desktop solution) à cultural change
- support server-side analysis and publishing
- easy to find, what is out there

- provide reference-data available for everybody
- provide recommendations for datasets (recommendations should come from the community via a rating option)
- Inclusion of data from private industry and private economy sector
- Publishing/access to governmental data
- Invite people on certain topics
- Support (e.g. USN) should be designed in a personal way à maybe local contact persons?
- Getting information, what are the standards for specific data.
- Provide a template system – curriculum design tool
- Ability to publish Jupyter-Notebooks (which can be linked in publications) + extend the trusted repositories to do this
- → cultural change
- Setup workflow frameworks and publish it
- Find the suitable license.
- Get an overview on licenses
- Show best practices
- Recognition and support with the things, which is already there
- Create a data rescue team
- Provide good and updated guidelines
- Support paper review process

Teaching Materials:

- materials should be provided in video format, not just texts (because there are users, don't like to read long explanations)
- knowledge transfer – best practice
- provide FAIR teaching materials, which can be easily reused and (with resp. to infrastructure) easy to be combined.
- Include DM into Master/PhD courses
- Discipline specific DM teaching offers

Others:

- data should be connected to tools, special support and available teaching materials (linkages)
- connection to other communities
- NFDI4Earth enforces credits, appreciation and recognition of researchers are of publish OpenAccess and FAIR data in science → cultural change
- → how is this possible. Incentives?
- Organisation of community events (small conferences, incl. abstracts) with respect to FDM and ESS (e.g. presentation of tools, blueprints, pilots, ...)
- Create an outreach plan → to reach Scientists and Researcher, but also in a political way (conferences, events, etc.)
- Create/provide Outreach Materials on NFDI4Earth
- Design as broker-service

- Overview on legal publication requirements
- Provide/create a common space
- Include users and codesign → expert needs
- NFDI4Earth drives the cultural change
- Specific domain problems need to be addressed
- Increase the awareness of OPENess

Breakout Group 3: What data and software 'products' do I envision in the NFDI4Earth? [Moderators: Stefan Frickenhaus, Auriol Degbelo].

The moderators asked four questions to participants to guide the discussion. The answers are summarized below.

Q1: Which data / software products would you like to publish via NFDI4Earth?

- Project-related datasets at research organizations (e.g. datasets / managed DBs produced in past research projects). These datasets are never going to get published (e.g. because the authors moved to something else, or there is no incentive to invest the effort of doing so. In short, funding for the project run out).
- Many regional data portals are available, but the awareness about their existence is still low
- Need for **scalable access and analysis to/of data**, also for non-experts in programming; software frameworks for R and Python needed
- **Governmental data** often hidden; opening Silos to exploration/ discovery, make governmental data citable, invite for co-authorship
- Geo scientific data from **companies** (e.g. analyse for provenance of sand in sediment cores): Shell opens data after 10 years (Netherlands)
- Visual data as **quick-looks**, with interactive user interface
- **Advisory systems** to link to other possibly relevant data
- Connect RDM-services to repositories to **support data publication** for multidisciplinary work
- Software framework **DASF to federate OGC data services** via web services and python, offers a common schema + API to various services

Q2: Which wishes do you have regarding added value for your published data / software?

- Increased visibility for the relevant community (the one who the data could benefit the most should know about it)
- Federated search
- Guide to tools and best practices, include **users RDM practice**
- Spatial search (user-defined polygons as search filter + in which spatial regions was X investigated in the past?)
- Data discovery: Recommendations of similar data

- Integration of bigger data with repositories
- Recommendations of experts to help me make sense of the data: After I have analyzed my data, I am at the step of the analysis where I get results, then I get a message: connect to this and that expert in statistical analysis / climate modelling
- **Suggestion tool** on knowledge graph
- **Open search foundation: semantic search** by asking questions

Q3: What software/framework should NFDI4Earth provide to support your work?

- Enable the search for software interfaces (e.g. APIs)
- Continuous integration: when the data is updated, update all services affected
- Tools that support in-house data management
- High-resolution data that would be useful for research, but that for some reasons are not free of charge (e.g. 20cm satellite data)
- Access to trained AI models (it would be nice to have both the data input and the model resulting from training the data for a specific prediction task)
- R- or Python-wrappers for data retrieval and analysis
- Access to ML capacity for non-experts
- Dataformat conversion service (Webbased, see NFDI4Chem)
- Metadata on Quality levels
- Tool to detect redundancy/ replicates across data sets

Q4: what would be an ideal workflow to publish your data / software via 4Earth?

- Reproducible publishing workflow: the data should be formatted for archiving before I start the analysis. I do the whole analysis in a private virtual environment. Once I'm done (e.g. after the peer-review process), I only have to switch my analysis to "public" and the whole environment (data + tools) is made available to all
- There should be an easy way to label my product (e.g. my GitHub repository as a 4Earth project)
- 4Earth support should come right at the beginning of the research data management life cycle (data management with forethought instead of as an afterthought)
- GitHub/GitLab integration for the products I develop
- Non-standard data/DBs from students, translation to curatable form for publication; e.g. Chemotion project for dataflow from Electronic Lab Books

Breakout Group 4: What are the potential of and needs from Pilots, Incubators, EduTrain and Academy? [Moderators: Jonas Kuppler, Veronika Grupp, Yu Feng, Fabian Przybylak, Effi Drews, Hilde Gödde, Farzaneh Sadeghi].

- High interest in the community in FAIR RDM, open & reproducible ESS and to be engaged in the NFDI4Earth.

- Engagement possibilities need to be more clearly and broadly communicated in the ESS community
 - Re-Design of homepage
 - Increase visibility of calls and their outcomes, clear communication of requirements and goals
 - Active and continuous communication of possibilities
- Great interest in education and training materials for students and researchers; especially early career
- Foster collaboration and engagement across ESS disciplines and other consortia

Breakout Group 5: If I could wish for an overarching theme for a pilot - what would it be? [Moderators: Miguel Mahecha, Fabian Gans, Lars Bernard].

Proposed Topics:

- Bridging NFDIs: interdisciplinary projects involving min. 2 consortia
- Combining datasets: different data centers; different formats or domains
- Provenance (reproducible workflows, data acquisition, ...)
- Visualisation of metadata and semantic data
- Mobilisation of data

Structural ideas:

- Split call: 1/2 thematic focus, 1/2 open call
- Flexfunds within Pilots for Spin-offs
- Future Rounds: use pilots to fill identified gaps within NFDI4Earth services

Breakout Group 6: What content would I like to see in the Interest Groups? Is what has been presented already sufficient - are we missing something? [Moderators: Hannes Thiemann, Dominik Hezel].

- IG to involve libraries
- Provenance, going beyond disciplinary boundaries
 - Incl. Reputation building trust
- Facilitate exchange between early career researchers (#IchbinHanna)
- As a corrective for the task areas
- How to onboard (namely HPC)
- Vision group, what is the "system", incl. technical aspects and people
- Search engines, repositories
- ONE metadata standard for research data in N4E
- Establish IGs for exchange with outside world
- Making data accessible (analogue data). Involve Repos
- Dealing with restrictive data (container solutions along the line of Ratswd)
- Examples for using big data. Lower barriers

- Terminologies
- Instruments and Samples and Persistent Identification
- To support cultural change (tools are there, will people follow)
- Enhance exchange between interest groups – concept needed
- How to find them?
- IG may complement TAs